

HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT
Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and
Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond
(GAPs)

Sweden's Return Turn: Legal Gaps, Policy Shifts and Reform Recommendations

Rebecca Thorburn Stern and Mudar Shakra
Uppsala University, Sweden

This policy brief draws on in-depth empirical and legal analysis carried out within the Horizon Europe GAPs project, particularly the Sweden country dossiers on legal and policy infrastructures of return (WP2) and return migration infrastructures (WP3). These studies systematically examine Sweden's regulations, policies, institutions, and statistics on return and readmission, situating national developments within broader EU frameworks and Pact reforms. Building on this evidence base, the brief distils the most salient findings into a concise set of policy-relevant insights and reform recommendations on return governance.

Introduction

For decades, Sweden was known for a relatively generous migration and asylum policy, but it has in more recent years undergone profound reorientation towards control and return. The watershed moment was the so-called refugee crisis of 2015, during which Sweden made what has often been described as a U-turn: from welcoming large numbers of refugees during the summer to, later that year, introducing border controls and temporary legislation aimed at significantly reducing arrivals and asylum applications. In the years that followed, this policy shift was further consolidated through a range of restrictive measures designed to make Sweden less attractive as a destination country, both for potential migrants and for foreign nationals already present in the country. These measures included, inter alia,

limitations on family reunification and the increased use of temporary residence permits.

This shift was further institutionalised following the 2022 general election, which resulted in a centre-right coalition government supported by the right-wing populist Sweden Democrats. The coalition's Tidö Agreement of 2022 laid out a markedly more restrictive migration agenda, encompassing stricter border controls, expanded use of detention, and broader grounds for revoking residence permits, and a general ambition to reduce protection-based asylum, to mention only a few examples.

While the "effectiveness" of returns had long featured on the political agenda, the Government during the period 2015–2021

took several initiatives aimed at increasing the number of enforced and assisted returns, which the Tidö Agreement now frames as a key priority. The Tidö Agreement constitutes yet another step in the shift away from reception towards return/removal, calling for a wide range of measures to ensure the enforcement of return decisions, including extended validity of return orders, tougher entry bans, increased use of detention and accelerated procedures. Since 2022, the Government has taken a number of steps to reform Swedish return policy along these lines, including legislative amendments, new instructions to the main migration authority – the Swedish Migration Agency – and increased budgetary allocations for return enforcement. At the same time, policies, legislation, and practice must continue to comply with Sweden’s international obligations and with fundamental rule-of-law principles such as legality, proportionality, and predictability.

From June 2026, an additional layer of complexity will be added to this tension between efficiency, legality, and humanitarian considerations, as the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum enters into force, introducing new return-related legislation, including the Return Border Procedure Regulation¹. Desk research and fieldwork on the Swedish return regime² conducted within the GAPS project between 2023 and 2025 have identified a number of structural and operational gaps in the current framework that undermine coherence and predictability

and risk impeding both effective and rights-compliant return procedures. The most policy-relevant findings and recommendations are summarized below.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1349 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 May 2024 establishing a return border procedure, and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1148.

² Thorburn Stern, R. & Shakra, M. (2024), Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Returns in Sweden – WP2 Country Dossier. GAPS: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond; Barthoma, S. & Tommos, S. (2025), Return Migration Infrastructures in Sweden – WP3 Country Dossier (v.1.). GAPS: De-centring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond.

Focus areas of Sweden's new migration policy

Swedish Government's website 2024.

Evidence and Analysis

Legal framework

The central legal instrument in Swedish migration law, including in the field of return, is the Aliens Act (2005:716), in force since 2006. Since then, the Act has been amended on numerous occasions, both to transpose EU law, such as the 2008 EU Return Directive³ and other instruments of the CEAS relevant for return – and to accommodate successive domestic policy shifts. The cumulative effect of these amendments has rendered the legislation increasingly opaque and difficult to navigate.

These challenges are further exacerbated in the return context by the fact that, when implementing the Return Directive, the Swedish Government chose not to transpose

several of the key terms and definitions contained in the Directive into the Aliens Act. As a result, Swedish law lacks explicit definitions of several core concepts set out in Article 3 of the Return Directive, including “irregular stay”, “return”, “removal”, and “assisted return”. Instead, migration authorities rely on interpretation, preparatory works, or case law to fill these gaps. The fact that the 2024 Return Border Procedure Regulation – applicable from June 2026 as part of the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum – employs the same concepts as the 2008 Return Directive does not appear to have prompted any reconsideration of the Swedish approach. The absence of clear legal definitions risks creating legal uncertainty for both decision-makers and affected individuals, weakening predictability and increasing the likelihood of inconsistent, arbitrary application or uneven practice along the return chain.

Expanding return categories and blurred voluntariness

³ Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals.

Despite the lack of clear legal definitions of key categories, Sweden operates with multiple de facto categories of return along a continuum from voluntary departure to forced removal. *Voluntary repatriation* targets legally resident migrants and relies on financial incentives to encourage return and the relinquishment of residence rights. With effect from January 2026, the amounts involved will be increased substantially, from SEK 10,000 per adult to SEK 350,000, with families eligible for up to SEK 600,000 in total. Re-establishment grants are directed at individuals whose residence permits are based on asylum-related grounds. By dramatically increasing the amounts available, the Government hopes to make the scheme more attractive particularly to groups considered “poorly integrated” or “long term dependent on welfare systems”, signalling a shift toward using large financial packages as a migration management tool.

Self-managed returns (non-assisted departures) apply to rejected asylum seekers who arrange their own departure using personal resources. This category often includes so-called “non-deportable” cases, where countries of origin refuse to cooperate with forced returns (for example Iran or Cuba). *Assisted voluntary return* – characterised by a form of enforced voluntariness – refers to practical, financial, and reintegration support provided by the Swedish Migration Agency to rejected asylum seekers or applicants who have withdrawn their asylum claims. This support is combined with systematic pressure through so-called “return information” or motivational interviews. Despite the label of voluntariness, such returns typically occur under conditions of structural duress, including the loss of accommodation and financial support and the threat of police enforcement. In 2024, approximately 8,300 persons with a return decision left Sweden voluntarily, representing an increase of around 700 persons compared to 2023, reflecting the policy pressure aspect.

At the coercive end of the spectrum, *forced removals* consist of police-enforced deportations, with or without escort, carried out by the Border Police and the Swedish Prison and Probation Service. The cost of forced removals is estimated to be approximately seven times higher than that of assisted voluntary returns, making overreliance on enforcement economically as well as normatively questionable. Taken together, these categories operate along a continuum with increasingly blurred boundaries between voluntary compliance and coercive enforcement. They are not discrete but overlapping, with the threat of coercion permeating all stages of the return process, albeit in different forms.

Weak data infrastructure and accountability gaps

A credible, rights-compliant return system depends on reliable, up-to-date, disaggregated, and publicly accessible data. In Sweden, the Migration Agency is responsible for collecting and consolidating return data, while the Police Authority – including the Border Police – collects data on border refusals, open enforcement cases, and removals executed. However, this information is not readily accessible on the websites of either authority. The difficulties involved in accessing and analysing Swedish return data are further compounded by the use of different categorisation systems and by as yet unexplained discrepancies between figures reported in the Migration Agency’s annual reports and those submitted to Eurostat. Limited data accessibility hampers external evaluation of return policies and practices, facilitates misinformation, and undermines evidence-based policymaking. Without comprehensive statistics, it becomes difficult to assess policy effectiveness, and mechanisms of accountability are weakened. Against this background, it is problematic that return data in Sweden are not collected in a systematic and coherent manner, making it difficult to draw definitive conclusions.

Figure 1: Return data 2015-2023. *Migrationsverket* (Adopted from Thorburn Stern & Shakra 2024).

Additional problems arise from inconsistent categorisation and unexplained discrepancies between data published in the Migration Agency’s annual reports and figures reported to Eurostat. The lack of standardised, transparent data – disaggregated by return category, legal basis, outcome, and reason for non enforcement (e.g. legal, medical, or practical impediments) – undermines evidence-based policymaking and allows contested narratives about “non return” to flourish with limited empirical grounding. This weak data infrastructure is a structural issue in an increasingly return driven policy environment.

Legal uncertainty and erosion of legitimate expectations

Consistency and foreseeability regarding the terms and conditions of residence permits are essential for individuals to make informed decisions about their future in the country of residence and for the legitimacy of migration governance. Abrupt rule changes to conditions, duration, or grounds for residence permits, particularly in the absence

of transitional provisions, destabilise legal status and may have severe consequences for individuals who have made life decisions based on existing rules. Moreover, sudden rule changes without adequate transition periods undermine the principles of legal certainty and the protection of legitimate expectations. Examples include the sharp increase, as of 1 November 2023, for work permits – from SEK 13,000 per month to at least 80 per cent of the median salary as published by Statistics Sweden (SEK 29,680 per month in 2025) – and a planned further increase to 90 per cent of the median salary from 1 June 2026. These changes have immediate consequences for workers and employers who invested on the basis of previous thresholds.

Similarly, the abolition of the humanitarian ground of “particularly distressing circumstances” on 1 December 2023 and the removal, as of 1 April 2025, of the possibility to “change tracks” from asylum seeker to temporary work permit, were implemented without transitional provisions. At the time of writing, proposals are also under

consideration to revoke permanent residence permits granted on asylum-related grounds, with entry into force envisaged for 1 January 2027.⁴ If adopted, these proposals would give affected individuals only a very limited window during which to apply for Swedish citizenship or otherwise face the prospect of remaining on short-term permits or leaving the country. Taken together, these measures weaken the protection of legitimate expectations, create instability for migrants who have complied with the rules, and risk fuelling onward irregularity and non-cooperation in return procedures.

A deterrence-driven reform agenda with limited rights focus

The implementation of the Tidö Agreement has generated a large number of reform proposals, some of which have already been adopted while others remain under consideration. These reforms share a common objective: to make Swedish migration policy more restrictive and Sweden less attractive to asylum seekers and other migrants, thereby explicitly using migration policy as a tool of deterrence. Return-related reforms include, inter alia, the abolition or significant extension of limitation periods for return decisions, the prolongation of entry bans, an intensified focus on identifying individuals staying irregularly in Sweden coupled with expanded police mandates, an increase in detention capacity, the use of development aid as leverage to promote returns and counter irregular migration, and the exclusion of irregular migrants from municipal financial assistance.

In this agenda, the human rights perspective and the lived experiences of migrants remain largely marginal. The overarching emphasis on state interests over individual rights raises serious questions as to the compatibility of

several proposals with Sweden's international human rights obligations. An additional concern is that the sheer volume, speed and overlap of proposed reforms make it difficult for parliamentarians, practitioners, researchers and civil society to gain a comprehensive overview of their cumulative effects and to assess their combined impact, increasing the risk of unintended and cumulative rights limitations.

In sum, Sweden operates a highly organised and legally dense return-enforcement regime whose effectiveness is increasingly undermined by operational dysfunctions, legal ambiguities, and growing ethical and human rights tensions. Understanding and addressing this paradox is crucial for policymakers seeking a return system that is not only firm, but also functional, lawful, and legitimate.

⁴ SOU (Government Commission of Inquiry Report) 2025:99 Ändring av permanent uppehållstillstånd för vissa utlänningar.

Policy Recommendations

Clarify meaning of key concepts

The implementation of the EU Migration and Asylum Pact will entail considerable changes to national migration regimes across EU Member States. The fact that the Pact is based on regulations rather than directives means that Member States are afforded less discretion in how EU law in this field is implemented. This is because regulations are binding legislative acts that apply in their entirety across the EU, whereas directives set objectives for Member States, which may be achieved through different national approaches. While regulations allow less room for interpretation, clarity at the national level regarding the meaning of key definitions used in legal texts, as well as in policy documents, guidelines, and other implementation instruments, will remain just as necessary after June 2026 as before in order to ensure compliance with EU law and to safeguard the legitimacy and transparency of return decisions.

Ensure transparency and accessibility in data management

The Migration Agency should be instructed to publish accurate, regularly updated, disaggregated, and easily accessible statistics on returns on its website. Currently, data on returns and readmissions is not systematically collected or presented in a coherent manner, making external evaluation of return policies and practices complicated and contributing to persistent uncertainties and the spread of disinformation. Data should at minimum be disaggregated to distinguish between different categories such as voluntary and forced returns, assisted and non-assisted returns, Dublin transfers, returns following rejected asylum applications, border refusals, and stock of irregular migrants, enforcement outcomes, and should identify the reasons why return decisions cannot be executed (such as practical, medical, or legal impediments).A

single, coherent data model, used consistently across the Migration Agency and the Police Authority, would significantly strengthen democratic accountability, enable evidence-based policymaking, and provide a factual basis for public debate.

Balance restrictiveness with rights protection and legal certainty

When designing and implementing stricter measures, the Government must ensure that fundamental human rights are respected and that the principle of proportionality is upheld. Consistency and foreseeability regarding the terms and conditions of residence permits are essential for individuals to make informed decisions about their future. Future legislative changes must include appropriate transitional provisions and safety-valve clauses for new circumstances that may arise. The Government must moreover conduct thorough analyses of the proportionality, long-term effects, and cumulative impact of all measures proposed to implement the Tidö Agreement before their adoption. The state's interest in pursuing a restrictive migration policy cannot justify overriding all other considerations. Restrictive rules must not become ends in themselves; they must be justified by legitimate aims and proportionate to those aims, with full consideration of their effects on integration, social cohesion, and fundamental rights protection.

Ensure informed consent in voluntary return programmes

Given the increasingly blurred boundaries between voluntary and coerced returns, clearer safeguards for informed consent are needed. Sweden should adopt explicit criteria for what constitutes a genuinely voluntary decision to return and ensure that all persons considering return have access to independent counselling and sufficient time to make an informed decision without undue pressure. Moreover, genuine voluntary return mechanisms that respect human dignity and individual agency should be prioritised,

rather than relying primarily on financial incentives and structural coercion to achieve

return

objectives..

Project identity

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Duration	2023-2026
Coordinators	Zeynep Sahin-Mencütek Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies zeynep.mencutek@bicc.de Soner Barthoma Uppsala University soner.barthoma@crs.uu.se
Consortium	Uppsala University (Sweden) Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (Germany) Stichting Radboud Universiteit (Netherlands) Ozyegin Universitesi (Turkey) Hammurabi Human Rights Organization (Iraq) Svenska Forskningsinstitutet i Istanbul (Sweden/Turkey) Hashemite University (Jordan) Ethniko Kentro Koinonikon Erevnon (Greece) Association Migration Internationale (Morocco) Toronto Metropolitan University (Canada) University of Nigeria (Nigeria) Bilim Organization for Research and Social Studies (Afghanistan) Uniwersytet Warszawski (Poland) Migration Matters EV (Germany) University of Sousse (Tunisia) SPIA UG (Germany) University of Glasgow (UK)
Further reading	For more detailed analysis of country dossiers and WP2/Sweden Country Report, please consult the GAPs project's website: : https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10943936

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Project summary

GAPs is a Horizon Europe research project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study of the drivers of return policies and the barriers to and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by decentering the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- analyses enablers of and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its approach with three innovative concepts:

- A focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance gaps;
- An analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU member states and third countries hinder cooperation on return and
- A trajectory approach which uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary research project (2023–2026) coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC) with 17 partners in 14 countries on four continents. GAPs’ fieldwork and desk research are conducted in several countries, including Afghanistan, Canada, Germany, Greece, Iraq, Jordan, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Morocco, Poland, Sweden, Tunisia, Türkiye, and the UK.